

Q^* -REGULAR SPACES

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of generalized regular space is called Q^* -regular space which is weaker than regularity. The relationships among strongly rg-regular, g-regular, regular, Q^* -regular, almost regular and softly regular spaces are investigated. Some of basic properties and characterizations of Q^* -regular spaces in the terms of other separation and countability axioms such as semi-regular, Hausdorff, separable, second countable and Lindelof spaces are obtained.

Key words: regular open, Q^* -open sets; softly regular, almost-regular, Q^* -regular spaces

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I. Introduction

In 1925, Urysohn [13] introduced and studied a new type of separation axiom, called Urysohn space. In 1926, Cartan [1] introduced and studied the concept of symmetric space. In topology, an R_0 -space is also known as a symmetric space. In 1937, Stone [12] introduced the notion of semi-regular spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 1958, Kuratowski [5] introduced a generalization of closed sets, called regularly-open and regularly-closed sets in general topology.

In 1963, Levine [6] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets and obtained their properties. In 1969, Singal and Arya [10] introduced a new class of separation axiom (namely almost regular space) in topological spaces which is weaker than regularity but it is equivalent to semi-regular spaces due to Stone [12] and investigated some basic properties with other separation axioms such as T_0 , T_1 , semi-regular, Hausdorff and k-spaces. In 1986, Munshi [7] introduced and studied some new class of separation axioms (named g-regular and g-normal spaces etc.) in topological spaces which are stronger than regularity and normality. In 1993, Palaniappan [9] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets, called regular generalized closed which is a weaker form of closed and g-closed sets and studied their properties. In 2010, Murugalingam and Lalitha [8] introduced and studied the concept of Q^* -open sets and obtained some properties of Q^* -open sets in topological spaces. In 2011, Gnanachandra and Thangavelu [2] introduced and studied the concepts of strongly rg-regular and strongly rg-normal spaces in topological spaces which are stronger than regularity and normality. In 2018, Kumar and Sharma [3] introduced and studied the concept of softly regular spaces in topological spaces which is a weak form of regularity and obtained some characterizations with regular, strongly rg-regular, weakly regular, almost regular, π -normal and quasi normal spaces. Recently, Kumar and Tomar [4] introduced and studied the concepts of Q^* -normal spaces in topological spaces which is weaker than normality and obtained their characterizations.

II. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **regularly-open** [5] if it is the interior of its own closure or, equivalently, if it is the interior of some closed set or equivalently, $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$. A subset A is said to be **regularly-closed** [5] if it is the closure of its own interior or, equivalently, if it is the closure of some open set or equivalently, $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$. Clearly, a set is regularly-open iff its complement is regularly-closed. The finite union of regularly open sets is said to be **π -open**. The

complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. Every regularly open (resp. regularly closed) set is π -open (resp. π -closed).

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **Q^* -closed** [8] if $\text{int}(A) = \emptyset$ and A is closed. The complement of a Q^* -closed set is said to be **Q^* -open**.

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (i) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [6] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (ii) **regular generalized closed** (briefly **rg-closed**) [9] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular-open in X .

The complement of A is g-closed (resp. rg-closed) set is said to be **g-open** (resp. **rg-open**). The family of all Q^* -closed (resp. Q^* -open) sets of a space X is denoted by $Q^*\text{-C}(X)$ (resp. $Q^*\text{-O}(X)$).

2.3 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \text{regular closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi\text{-closed} & & & & \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & & & \\
 Q^*\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \text{closed} & \Rightarrow & \text{g-closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi\text{g-closed} \Rightarrow \text{rg-closed}
 \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then

- (i) regular closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (ii) π -closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (iii) closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (iv) Q^* -closed sets are : $\emptyset, \{c\}$.
- (v) g-closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (vi) π g-closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (vii) rg-closed sets are : $\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.

2.5 Example. In \mathbb{R} with usual metric, finite sets are Q^* -closed but not regular closed. $[0, 1]$ is regular closed but not Q^* -closed. Hence regular closed and Q^* -closed sets are independent of each other.

2.6 Definition. A space X is said to be a **Urysohn space** [13] if for every pair of distinct points x and y , there exist open sets U and V such that $x \in U, y \in V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

2.7 Definition. A space X is said to be **symmetric space** (or **R_0 -space**) [1] if for any two distinct points x and y of $X, x \in \text{cl}(\{y\})$ implies that $y \in \text{cl}(\{x\})$.

2.8 Definition. A topological space X is called **T_{Q^*} -space** if every Q^* -closed set in it is closed set.

2.9 Definition. A space X is said to be **g-normal** [7] if for every pair of disjoint g-closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2.10 Definition. A space X is said to be **strongly rg-normal** [2] if for every pair of disjoint rg-closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2.11- Definition. A space X is said to be **Q^* -normal** [4] if for every pair of disjoint Q^* -closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram:

$$\text{rg-normality} \Rightarrow \text{g-normality} \Rightarrow \text{normality} \Rightarrow Q^*\text{-normality}$$

Where none of the implications are reversible.

III. Q^* -regular spaces

3.1 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **Q^* -regular** if for every Q^* -closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.2 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **softly regular** [3] if for every π -closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.3 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **almost regular** [10] if for every regularly closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.4 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **g-regular** [7] if for every g-closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.5 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **strongly rg-regular** [2] if for every rg-closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.6 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **semi-regular** [12] if for each point x of the space and each open set U containing x , there is an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(V)) \subset U$.

3.7 Theorem. Every regular space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Let X be a regular space. Let F be any Q^* -closed set in X and a point $x \in X$ such that $x \notin F$. Since we know that every Q^* -closed set is closed. So, F is closed and $x \notin F$. Since X is a regular space, there exists a pair of disjoint open sets G and H such that $F \subset G$ and $x \in H$. Hence X is a Q^* -regular space.

3.8 Theorem [7]. Every g-regular space is regular hence Q^* -regular.

3.9 Theorem [2]. Every strongly rg-regular space is regular hence Q^* -regular.

By the definitions and results stated above, we have the following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

3.10 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Consider the closed set $\{b, c\}$ and a point 'a' such that $a \notin \{b, c\}$. Then $\{b, c\}$ and $\{a\}$ are disjoint open sets such that $\{b, c\} \subset \{b, c\}$, $a \in \{a\}$ and $\{b, c\} \cap \{a\} = \phi$. Similarly, for the closed set $\{a\}$ and a point 'c' such that $c \notin \{a\}$. Then there exist open sets $\{a\}$ and $\{b, c\}$ such that $\{a\} \subset \{a\}$, $c \in \{b, c\}$ and $\{a\} \cap \{b, c\} = \phi$. It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is regular as well as softly regular space.

3.11 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. If we take a point 'a' and an open set $V = \{a\}$, then $\text{cl}(V) = \{a, c\}$ and a regularly-open set $U = X$. So by the definition of weakly regular space $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$, where V be an open set and U be a regularly-open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, c\} \subset X$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular. If we take a point 'a' and a regularly-closed set $A = \{b, c\}$ does not containing the point 'a', there donot exist disjoint open sets containing the point 'a' and a regularly-closed set $A = \{b, c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not almost-regular.

3.12 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular but not partly-regular. If we take a point 'a' and an open set $V = \{a\}$, then $\text{cl}(V) = \{a, c\}$. Let $U = \{a, b\}$ be any π -open set. So by the definition of partly-regular space $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$, where V be an open set and U be a π -open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, c\} \not\subset \{a, b\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not partly-regular.

3.13 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular but not softly-regular. Let $A = \{c\}$ be any π -closed set doesnot containing a point 'a' i.e. $a \notin \{c\}$, there do not exist disjoint open sets containing the point 'a' and the π -closed set $A = \{c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not softly-regular.

3.14 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is almost regular but not strongly rg-regular. If we take a point 'a' and $F = \{b\}$ be any rg-closed set. Then there do not exist disjoint open sets containing the point 'a' and rg-closed set $F = \{b\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not strongly rg-regular.

IV. Characterizations of Q^* -regular spaces

4.1 Theorem. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , the following properties are equivalent:

- (a) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular.
- (b) For every $x \in X$ and every Q^* -open set U containing x , there exists an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.
- (c) For every Q^* -closed set A , the intersection of all the closed neighbourhood of A is A .
- (d) For every set A and a Q^* -open set B such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$, there exists an open set F such that $A \cap F \neq \emptyset$ and $\text{cl}(F) \subset B$.
- (e) For every nonempty set A and Q^* -closed set B such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$, there exist disjoint open sets L and M such that $A \cap L \neq \emptyset$ and $B \subset M$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Suppose (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular. Let $x \in X$ and U be a Q^* -open set containing x so that $X - U$ is Q^* -closed. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular, there exist open sets V_1 and V_2 such that $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$ and $x \in V_1, X - U \subset V_2$. Take $V = V_1$. Since $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset, V \subset X - V_2 \subset U$ that implies $\text{cl}(V) \subset \text{cl}(X - V_2) = X - V_2 \subset U$. Therefore $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be Q^* -closed set and $x \notin A$. Since A is Q^* -closed, $X - A$ is Q^* -open and $x \in X - A$. Therefore by (b) there exists an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset X - A$. Thus $A \subset X - \text{cl}(V) \subset X - V$ and $x \notin X - V$. Consequently $X - V$ is a closed neighborhood of A .

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ and B be Q^* -open. Let $x \in A \cap B$. Since B is Q^* -open, $X - B$ is Q^* -closed and $x \notin X - B$. By our assumption, there exists a closed neighborhood V of $X - B$ such that $x \notin V$. Let $X - B \subset U \subset V$, where U is open. Then $F = X - V$ is open such that $x \in F$ and $A \cap F \neq \emptyset$. Also $X - U$ is closed and $\text{cl}(F) = \text{cl}(X - V) \subset X - U \subset B$. This shows that $\text{cl}(F) \subset B$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Suppose $A \cap B = \emptyset$, where A is non-empty and B is Q^* -closed. Then $X - B$ is Q^* -open and $A \cap (X - B) \neq \emptyset$. By (d), there exists an open set L such that $A \cap L \neq \emptyset$, and $L \subset \text{cl}(L) \subset X - B$. Put $M = X - \text{cl}(L)$. Then $B \subset M$ and L, M are open sets such that $M = X - \text{cl}(L) \subset (X - L)$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let B be Q^* -closed and $x \notin B$. Then $B \cap \{x\} = \emptyset$. By (e), there exist disjoint open sets L and M such that $L \cap \{x\} \neq \emptyset$ and $B \subset M$. Since $L \cap \{x\} \neq \emptyset, x \in L$. This proves that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular.

4.2 Theorem. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular if and only if for each Q^* -closed set F of (X, \mathfrak{T}) and each $x \in X - F$, there exist open sets U and V of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof: Let F be a Q^* -closed set in (X, \mathfrak{T}) and $x \notin F$. Then there exist open sets U_x and V such that $x \in U_x, F \subset V$ and $U_x \cap V = \emptyset$. This implies that $U_x \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Since $\text{cl}(V)$ is closed and $x \notin \text{cl}(V)$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular, there exist open sets G and H of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in G, \text{cl}(V) \subset H$ and $G \cap H = \emptyset$. This implies $\text{cl}(G) \cap H = \emptyset$. Take $U = U_x \cap G$. Then U and V are open sets of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$, since $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) \subset \text{cl}(G) \cap H = \emptyset$.

Conversely, suppose for each Q^* -closed set F of (X, \mathfrak{T}) and each $x \in X - F$, there exist open sets U and V of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U, F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Now $U \cap V \subset \text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Therefore $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Q^* -regular.

4.3 Theorem. In a Q^* -regular space X , every pair consisting of a compact set A and a disjoint Q^* -closed set B can be separated by open sets.

Proof. Let X be Q^* -regular space and let A be a compact set, B be a Q^* -closed set with $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Since X is Q^* -regular space, for each $x \in A$, there exist disjoint open sets U_x and V_x such that $x \in U_x, B \subset V_x$. Clearly $\{U_x : x \in A\}$ is an open covering of the compact set A . Since A is compact, there exists a finite subfamily $\{U_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ which covers A . It follows that $A \subset \cup \{U_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and $B \subset \cap \{V_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3,$

....., n }. Put $U = \cup \{U_{xi} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and $V = \cap \{V_{xi} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, then $U \cap V = \phi$. For, if $x \in U \cap V \Rightarrow x \in U_{xj}$ for some j and $x \in V_{xi}$ for every i . This implies that $x \in U_{xj} \cap V_{xi}$, which is a contradiction to $U_{xj} \cap V_{xi} = \phi$. Thus U and V are disjoint open sets containing A and B respectively.

V. Relations of Q^* -regular spaces with Some Separation Axioms

5.1 Theorem [10]. Every almost regular, semi-regular space is regular.

5.2 Corollary. Every almost regular, semi-regular space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is Q^* -regular.

5.3 Corollary. Every softly regular, semi-regular space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every softly regular space is almost regular.

5.4 Theorem [11]. Every normal, symmetric space is regular.

5.5 Corollary. Every normal, symmetric space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is Q^* -regular.

5.6 Corollary. Every g -normal, symmetric space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every g -normal space is normal.

5.7 Corollary. Every rg -normal, symmetric space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every rg -normal space is normal.

5.8 Theorem [11]. Every compact Hausdorff space is regular.

5.9 Corollary. Every compact Hausdorff space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is Q^* -regular.

5.10 Corollary. Every compact Urysohn space is Q^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every Urysohn space is Hausdorff.

VI. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of generalized regular space is called Q^* -regular space which is weaker than regularity. The relationships among strongly rg -regular, g -regular, regular, Q^* -regular, almost regular and softly regular spaces are investigated. Some of basic properties and characterizations of Q^* -regular spaces in the terms of other separation and countability axioms such as semi-regular, Hausdorff, separable, second countable and Lindelof spaces are obtained. This idea can be extended to topological ordered, bitopological, bitopological ordered and fuzzy topological spaces etc.

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